

STUDY OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE INFLUENCE OF ENDOTHELIN 1 AND VASCULAR ENDOTHELIAL GROWTH FACTOR IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE WHO UNDERWENT REVASCULARIZATION

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Abstract

Cardiovascular diseases remain the leading cause of death worldwide, with ischemic heart disease (IHD) being the most common. Ischemia-induced angiogenesis is a process in which vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and endothelin 1 play a critical role. Understanding the role of VEGF and endothelin 1 in the physiological and pathological processes of the heart is essential for research into the association of VEGF and endothelin 1 with cardiovascular diseases.

Keywords: endothelin-1, vascular endothelial growth factor, coronary heart disease, revascularization

Coronary heart disease (CHD) is classified as a multifactorial disease, the development of which is the result of a complex interaction of hereditary predisposition and environmental factors. Since heredity is an independent risk factor for the disease, the need to include genetic markers in calculations to predict the risk of developing CHD is now becoming obvious. There are racial and ethnic differences in gene polymorphism, which explains the relevance of the study in the Uzbek population [1]. Analysis of the association of a gene with a disease and subsequent assessment of individual genetic risk are important for developing a differentiated approach to the prevention and treatment of this pathology depending on the hereditary predisposition of a particular patient. The relevance of the problem under consideration is due to the need for further study of the causes and subtle mechanisms of ischemic and / or post-infarction dysfunction of the left ventricle, the importance of improving the quality of diagnosis and treatment of complications of myocardial ischemia – chronic heart failure (CHF). Disclosure of the role of genetic factors in the formation and progression of CHF has a significant impact on understanding its pathophysiology. In addition, genetic technologies currently available open up new prospects for determining the prognosis of CHF, developing new approaches to treatment and evaluating the effectiveness of therapy [1, 3, 4].

Based on the current understanding of the pathogenesis of chronic heart failure and the mechanisms that underlie its initiation, it is possible to identify groups of so-called candidate genes, the products of which may be directly or indirectly involved in the development of this pathology. The development of an early preclinical diagnostics strategy is currently one of the most relevant progressive approaches that determines the prospects and possibilities of predicting and conducting preventive therapy for pathology using genetic predictors [5, 6]. Genetic studies currently available for cardiology practice allow for an objective assessment of the prospects and effectiveness of treatment, thereby opening up new possibilities for

pharmacogenetics and pharmacogenomics that can improve the quality of life and survival of patients with CHF [1, 4].

Material and methods.

The study included patients with coronary heart disease, angina pectoris II-III FC, complicated by CHF II-III FC according to NYHA. 51 patients (26 men and 25 women), aged 45 to 70 years (mean age 58.7 ± 4.25 years) were examined. The control group consisted of 20 people (mean age 54.7 ± 3.2 years) without cardiovascular pathology and severe chronic diseases.

The diagnosis of coronary heart disease was established on the basis of complaints, anamnesis (angina attacks, previous myocardial infarction, rhythm and conduction disturbances, signs of heart failure: shortness of breath, suffocation, palpitations, fatigue); physical examination data (orthopnea, lower limb edema, acrocyanosis, enlarged cardiac borders, muffled heart sounds, systolic murmur at the apex of the heart, arrhythmia, moist rales in the lungs); data from instrumental examination methods (ischemic, cicatricial changes, rhythm and conduction disturbances on ECG, signs of systolic and/or diastolic dysfunction, hypokinesia zones on echocardiography).

Electrocardiography was performed on the first day of the patient's admission to the hospital. A stationary electrocardiograph «Bioset» (Germany) was used.

Echocardiographic examination was performed on the ACCUVIXV20 device (Korea), in M- and B-modes in standard echocardiographic positions according to the recommendations of the American Society of Echocardiography (ASE) (Schiller N.B. et al., 1989). The structural parameters of the heart were studied: end-systolic dimension (ESD), end-diastolic dimension (EDD), interventricular septum (IVS) and posterior wall (PW) thickness of the LV. The parameters characterizing the functional state of the left ventricle were calculated: end-systolic volume (ESV), end-diastolic volume (EDV). The systolic function of the LV was studied by the value of the ejection fraction (EF), calculated according to the method of L. Teichholtz.

The determination of VEGF and endothelin-1 in blood plasma was carried out by the enzyme immunoassay method on the solid-phase analyzer «HumareaderSingle» (Germany).

The collection of blood samples from patients was carried out with the consent of the probands. Venous

blood in the amount of 1 ml was collected in 0.1 ml of sodium citrate solution and stored at minus 20° C.

Research results.

In all patients with coronary heart disease complicated by heart failure of different functional classes and in individuals in the control group, the level of endothelin-1 was determined (Table 1).

Table 1.

Endothelin-1 level in the blood of patients with coronary heart disease depending on the functional class of CHF

Indicator	CHF II FC (n=32)	CHF III FC (n=18)	Control group (n=20)
Endothelin – 1, fmol/ml	0.75±0.04**	1.12±0.1*	0.4±0.01

Note: *- p<0.05 when compared with the control group and with CHFIIFC; **- p<0.05 when compared with the control group and with CHFIII FC

In the control group, the average endothelin-1 level was 0.4±0.01 fmol/ml. In patients of groups 1 and 2, its content in the blood increased proportionally to the severity of FC CHF. Thus, in group 1 with FC II CHF, the endothelin-1 level was almost 2 times higher than in the control group, amounting to 0.75±0.04 fmol/ml. With a more severe course of CHF – FC III, the endothelin-1 level reached 1.12±0.1 fmol/ml, almost three times higher (p<0.05) than that in the control group. It was found that in patients with an unfavorable course of the disease (development of cardiovascular events during the year of observation), the initial level of endothelin-1 in the blood serum was 42.2% higher than this indicator in the group of patients with a favorable course. After 12 months of observation, patients with an unfavorable course of the disease showed a significant increase in endothelin-1 expression (by 1.22 times) compared to the initial level (p < 0.05), while in patients in the group with a favorable course, the activity level of this peptide remained unchanged over time.

Thus, the level of endothelin-1 over 0.75 fmol / ml allowed us to predict adverse cardiovascular events in patients with CHF with the highest probability (sensitivity – 84%, specificity – 65%).

When assessing the likelihood of adverse cardiovascular events (CHF progression, recurrent MI, mortality) depending on the level of endothelin-1 at the beginning of the observation period, they were divided into two groups: the first group – patients with a serum protein level of < 0.75 fmol / ml, the second group – patients with a serum endothelin-1 level of > 0.75 fmol / ml. It turned out that adverse cardiovascular events during the year developed in the 1st group in only 5 (19%) patients, while in the 2nd group – in 18 (55%) patients, i.e. almost 3 times more often. Consequently, the probability of developing adverse cardiovascular events during the year with an endothelin-1 expression level of >0.75 fmol/ml is significantly (p=0.0067) higher than with an endothelin-1 level of <0.75 fmol/ml.

Analysis of the relationship between the indicators of the structural and functional state of the LV according to EchoCG data and the level of expression of endothelin-1 showed a significant negative correlation between the LV ejection fraction and the concentration of endothelin-1 in the serum (r = - 0.54, p < 0.05), as well as a positive correlation between the level of protein expression and the size of the LV cavities (end systolic and end diastolic) and the thickness of the LV walls (Table 2).

Table 2.

Correlation relationship between endothelin-1 expression and indicators of the structural and functional state of the LV

Indicator	Endothelin – 1	p
LA, mm	0,37	0,0035
IVS, mm	0,51	<0,0001
Posterior wall of the left ventricle, mm	0,53	<0,0001
EDS, mm	0,41	0,0011
ESS, mm	0,49	0,0001
EV LV, %	-0,54	<0,0001

Thus, early assessment of the blood level of this metabolite is important not only for reliable prediction of the course of CHF, but also for assessing the effectiveness of pathogenetic preventive therapy. Further accumulation of clinical and experimental data will clarify

the physiological and pathological role of endothelins in the development of ischemic dysfunction of the LV myocardium and the progression of CHF.

Further, we analyzed the level of VEGF in stratifying the risk of developing CHF in patients with ischemic and/or post-infarction cardiac dysfunction (Table 3).

Table 3.

Features of VEGF level in the group of patients with CHF and in the control group

Indicator	Control group (n=20) 1	Patients with coronary heart disease complicated by CHF FC 2 (n=34) 2	Patients with coronary heart disease complicated by CHF FC 3 (n=20) 3	P 1-2	P 1-3	P 2-3
VEGF pg/ml	256.5±6.7	331.7±10.9	251.3±14.2	<0.05	ND	<0.05

It was established that in patients with CHF, the level of VEGF in the blood plasma, depending on the FC, differed significantly from the control values. At the same time, in patients with FC 2 CHF, compared with healthy individuals, the production of this factor increased by 1.3 times ($p = 0.0093$), with FC 3 – it did

not differ significantly. Analysis of the relationship between the indicators of the structural and functional state of the LV according to EchoCG data and the level of growth factors showed a reliable negative correlation between the KDR and KSR with the concentration of VEGF and a positive relationship with LV EF ($r = 0.59$, $p < 0.0001$) (Table 4).

Table 4.

Correlation relationship of echocardiography parameters with the content of vascular endothelial growth factor in the blood of patients with coronary heart disease.

Parameters	VEGF	P
EDR (mm)	-0.50	0.0035
EDR (mm)	-0.57	<0.0001
EF (%)	0.59	<0.0001
LA (mm)	-0.36	0.0011
IVS (mm)	-0.60	0.0001
LVP (mm)	-0.51	<0.0001

Thus, the analysis of the conducted study allowed us to establish important pathophysiological determinants influencing the functioning of the ischemic myocardium in conditions of increasing heart failure and determining the characteristics of its course. Analysis of data related to the study of the influence of vascular endothelial growth factor on the severity and nature of the course of CHF showed that in patients with CHF 2 FC, VEGF production significantly increases compared to the control group, decreasing with increasing severity of the disease. It was shown that the expression levels of growth factors correlated quite closely with LV EDD, LVEF, and ESR, reflecting the diastolic and systolic functions of the heart. The data we obtained allow us to classify endothelial growth factor and endothelin-1 as important biomarkers of both the development and progression of CHF in patients with coronary heart disease.

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